

Faith in Service Systems: Dynamics of Cultural-Based Practitioners in Creating Shared Spaces among State, Market, and Religion

Yaoharee Lahtee

Araya Nikah Social Enterprise Co., Ltd.

Email: arayawedding@gmail.com

Abstract

This article examines the role of **Cultural-Based Practitioners (CBP)** who operate at the intersection of the state, market, and religion, amidst the rapid transformations driven by the ASEAN digital economy. The author posits that faith is not an impediment to development but rather a profound ethical and human-centric foundation for creating service systems that honor religious identity without commodifying it. The paper proposes elevating the role of these practitioners, framing them as a form of "**Living Soft Infrastructure**" essential for sustainably supporting the region's dynamic economic and cultural landscape.

Keywords: Cultural-Based Practitioners (CBP), Faith-Based Capital, Cultural Governance, Living Soft Infrastructure, Service Systems

1. Introduction: Valorizing Faith-Based Capital in the Digital Economy

Since 2008, the ASEAN digital economy has profoundly reshaped social and cultural structures (Hong Kong Trade Development Council [HKTDC], 2023). Amidst this dynamism, faith continues to function as a crucial form of social capital, fostering trust and ethical values (Battour & Ismail, 2016; Putnam, 2000; Sen, 1999). However, some literature tends to reduce faith to a mere marketing commodity.

This article argues that faith-based capital can be transformed into assessable and verifiable service systems (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2022). This is achieved through the framework of "**Cultural-Based Practitioners (CBP)**", a concept integrating three core competencies: **cultural skills**, functioning as a **cultural bridge**, and upholding **cultural governance**. Together, these competencies form a "**Living Soft Infrastructure**" (cf. Bourdieu, 1986).

The case of Araya Nikah Social Enterprise prompts an inquiry into how an individual initiative expanded into a service system trusted by a client

network across 32 countries. Concurrently, Taiwan, with a Muslim population of only 0.3%, impressively climbed from 10th to 3rd in the Global Muslim Travel Index within a few years (Mastercard-CrescentRating, 2024; Taiwan Tourism Administration, 2025).

Therefore, this article aims to: (1) explain the transformation of faith-based capital in the context of the ASEAN digital economy; (2) propose the CBP framework at both individual and institutional levels; (3) substantiate the framework using case studies from Thailand and Taiwan; and (4) offer actionable policy recommendations.

This research is developed from the author's position as a **practitioner-researcher**. It blends direct field experience with established theoretical frameworks to generate knowledge that is practically applicable and sustainable. The author employs an **autoethnographic** approach to present direct observations from working with clients, families, and partners from diverse cultural backgrounds. This methodology was chosen to authentically capture the "voice of practice" and propose a new conceptual framework rooted in lived experience. This work does not claim to be a final answer but a starting point for scholarly dialogue and further development. Its core objective is to offer a novel conceptual proposition, grounded in practice, that illuminates the agency of ordinary individuals working in contested cultural spaces—a phenomenon not yet adequately explained in existing literature.

2. Conceptual Framework and Methodology

As a practitioner working in the culturally contested space of cross-cultural marriage, the author observed that facilitating services amidst diversity requires constant adaptation, deep listening, and finding common ground. The concept of "cultural skills," articulated by Chaiwat Satha-Anand, provided an academic term for these field practices.

However, experience revealed the limitations of cultural skills alone. Within Muslim communities, cultural differences are not confined to inter-religious dynamics but also exist *within* the faith, stemming from varied interpretations of truth. Intense group cohesion can paradoxically amplify these internal divisions, leading to mistrust. This observation aligns with the concept of intercultural competence, which suggests that communication skills are insufficient to resolve structural conflicts without supporting value frameworks and social mechanisms (Deardorff, 2006).

Participation in a "Conflict Transformation" workshop at Mahidol University's Institute of Human Rights and Peace Studies introduced the term "**cultural bridge**." While potent, its practical application presented challenges. The facilitator's mandated neutrality often reduced individuals to mere "dialogue

tools," neglecting genuine emotions, especially when overt injustice occurred. Furthermore, the emotional labor on the facilitator—managing the atmosphere, supporting conflicting parties, and suppressing reactions to injustice—was immense. This problem is magnified by the scarcity of formally trained facilitators compared to the ubiquity of cultural clashes globally. Functioning solely as a bridge cannot create deep, sustainable change, an observation that resonates with Lederach (1997), who argued that peace processes focused on dialogue without addressing emotional and justice dimensions cannot achieve positive peace.

Subsequently, training on "Creating Social Impact Through ESG" highlighted the importance of organizational governance. This experience illuminated a recurring field problem: a lack of transparency. In cultural spaces, this opacity can breed a sense of being co-opted from both sides. Non-Muslim families and organizations worried that religious values would subsume their culture, while some Muslims feared their own culture was being altered.

To address this, the author developed and implemented the concept of "**Cultural Governance**," emphasizing transparency, accountability, and respect for diversity as its core tenets. This framework, reflecting principles of good governance (Moore, 1995) and multicultural management (Kymlicka, 2015), was well-received by both Muslim and non-Muslim stakeholders, leading to tangible interfaith collaborations.

Beyond Western frameworks, this research is informed by Islamic thought, particularly *maqāṣid al-sharīah* (the higher objectives of Islamic law) and *fiqh al-muāmalāt* (the jurisprudence of social transactions), which prioritize justice, transparency, and peaceful coexistence (Kamali, 2008; Auda, 2010). These values align with the field observation that sustainable coexistence requires more than just cultural skills or bridging.

Based on these insights, the author concludes that no single component is sufficient. Cultural skills, cultural bridging, and cultural governance each have limitations. However, when integrated and practiced simultaneously, they form a "**Living Soft Infrastructure**" capable of transforming faith and cultural capital into verifiable social and economic value.

2.1. Theoretical Contribution

This study engages with key theoretical frameworks, including Cultural Capital (Bourdieu, 1986), Social Capital (Putnam, 2000), Public Value (Moore, 1995), Service-Dominant Logic (Vargo & Lusch, 2004), and Cultural Intermediaries (Maguire & Matthews, 2012). While foundational, these theories have limitations in explaining practitioner-level dynamics. This research proposes the CBP framework—uniting cultural skills, cultural bridging, and cultural governance—to conceptualize the creation of a "Living Soft

Infrastructure" that produces transparent and verifiable socio-economic outcomes.

2.2. Definition: Cultural-Based Practitioners (CBP)

Cultural-Based Practitioners (CBP) are individuals, groups, or institutions that systematically integrate **cultural skills**, the role of a **cultural bridge**, and **cultural governance** in unison. They design and operate a Living Soft Infrastructure within culturally contested spaces, generating demonstrable and verifiable socio-economic outcomes measured by contextually appropriate indicators.

2.3. Methodology

This research presents a **proposed conceptual framework** synthesized from field practice. The core argument is that while cultural skills, bridging, or governance are insufficient on their own, their simultaneous application constitutes a Living Soft Infrastructure that valorizes faith and cultural capital.

The study employs **Autoethnography** (Ellis, 2004; Bochner & Ellis, 2016), drawing on three primary sources:

1. **Researcher's field notes (2022–2025):** Reflecting observations and interpretations from working with cross-cultural couples and families.
2. **Internal organizational documents:** Including activity reports, client forms, and ESG reports from Araya Nikah Social Enterprise Co., Ltd. (2025), which verify systematic practices.
3. **External case studies:** Including Taiwan's Muslim-friendly tourism policy (Mastercard-CrescentRating, 2024) and Singapore's halal standards (MUIS, 2023) as regional best practices.

To mitigate potential bias from the researcher's embedded position, the study utilizes **reflexivity** through personal journaling and iterative writing to check observations against theory. **Peer debriefing** with colleagues provided alternative perspectives to reduce personal bias. To enhance qualitative credibility, the research employs **integrated verification**, connecting data from field notes, internal documents, and external cases. This ensures the concept of Living Soft Infrastructure is empirically grounded. The framework is not presented as a definitive theory but as a conceptual proposition open to critique and further development.

2.4. Use of AI Tools

This research utilized AI-assisted tools for **editorial assistance only**, such as organizing structure, proofreading English phrasing, and formatting text to meet international academic standards. AI had no role in data interpretation, generating findings, or shaping the research direction. Its use was solely to

enhance the clarity and systematic presentation of the work, which remains rigorously grounded in the practitioner-researcher's fieldwork.

3. Analysis of Findings: The Role of CBP

This research confirms that the complete integration of three core competencies—cultural skills, cultural bridging, and cultural governance—gives rise to a **Living Soft Infrastructure**. This structure effectively transforms faith and cultural capital into measurable socio-economic outcomes while mitigating the effects of negative social capital, such as prejudice, inequality, and exclusion (Putnam, 2000; Sen, 1999).

3.1. State Policy Level: Taiwan

The Taiwan Tourism Administration demonstrates how a state can systematically create a Muslim-friendly environment, even with a small Muslim population, by integrating the three CBP competencies:

- **Cultural Skills:** Training officials and tourism operators on Muslim cultural and religious needs.
- **Cultural Bridge:** Providing halal food options and prayer rooms in public spaces, bridging the gap between visitor needs and local infrastructure.
- **Cultural Governance:** Communicating policies in a way that respects and avoids disrupting local community life, ensuring transparency and inclusivity.

The result is Taiwan's consistent rise in the Global Muslim Travel Index (GMTI) (Taiwan Tourism Administration, 2025; Mastercard-CrescentRating, 2024).

3.2. Institutional Level: Singapore (MUIS)

Singapore's Majlis Ugama Islam Singapura (MUIS) exemplifies an institutional CBP, systematically connecting the "state-market-religion" nexus through its halal certification standards (MUIS, 2020; 2021). This is achieved through:

- **Cultural Skills:** Designing clear halal guidelines and handbooks that translate religious requirements into practical business contexts.
- **Cultural Bridge:** Acting as an intermediary between the government, private sector, and consumers to reduce uncertainty and build trust.
- **Cultural Governance:** Implementing transparent auditing processes and public reporting mechanisms.

Consequently, MUIS standards have gained international recognition, contributing to Singapore's high ranking in the GMTI (Mastercard-CrescentRating, 2024).

3.3. Individual Level (ASEAN State): Halimah Yacob, Singapore

Born to an Indian-Muslim father and a Malay-Muslim mother, Halimah Yacob identifies as Malay (The Straits Times, 2017). Early in her career as a labor lawyer, she protected the rights of all workers, reflecting **cultural skills** and a commitment to fairness analogous to **cultural governance** at the community level (Moore, 1995).

In 2013, she became Singapore's first female Speaker of Parliament, providing a platform for minority voices, particularly Malay Muslims, in a Chinese-majority political arena—a clear **cultural bridge** role (Deardorff, 2006).

Her ascension to the presidency in 2017 without a contested election drew criticism ("#NotMyPresident") (Reuters, 2017). However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, she authorized the use of tens of billions of dollars from the nation's past reserves. Her public declarations of the amounts drawn and their specific purposes ensured the process was transparent and accountable (Ministry of Finance Singapore, 2020–2022). Halimah's case demonstrates that by embodying all three elements of CBP, she successfully built trust and acceptance in a pluralistic society.

3.4. Individual Level (Thai State): Pateemoh Sadeeyamu, Thailand

Born in 1965 in Yala province, Pateemoh Sadeeyamu grew up in a local Muslim family in Thailand's southern border region. She began her career in the Ministry of Interior in 1994, serving in various roles before being appointed Governor of Pattani Province in 2022—the first female Muslim governor in Thai history (Thansettakij, 2022; The Standard, 2022).

Her early career reflects **cultural skills** through communication with diverse ethnic and religious groups. Her identity as a Muslim woman in the province's highest office—a position historically inaccessible to this demographic—allowed her to function as a **cultural bridge**, connecting Muslim citizens' voices to the central government. As governor, she has addressed complex issues of security, economy, and coexistence. Her open, transparent, and accountable policymaking for all religious communities exemplifies **cultural governance**, enhancing the credibility of the state bureaucracy in a fragile region (Moore, 1995; UNDP, 2022). Pateemoh's career shows that even in an "unconventional" role, the complete application of CBP principles can build trust in a sensitive multicultural context.

3.5. Local Individual/Legal Entity Level: Araya Nikah Social Enterprise, Thailand

The case of Araya Nikah Social Enterprise demonstrates that when an individual or organization fully integrates the three CBP competencies, it yields verifiable economic and social outcomes. These include developing curricula for cross-cultural families, creating safe communication spaces, and publishing transparent reports. This integration allowed the organization to

grow from an individual effort into a social enterprise with an international footprint. However, the case also reveals limitations: when faced with complex issues like human trafficking or cross-border documentation, individual or entity-level actions are insufficient. Sustaining the "Living Soft Infrastructure" requires collaboration with state, institutional, and network-based support.

3.6. The Living Soft Infrastructure

Across these cases, the "Living Soft Infrastructure" emerges when all three CBP competencies are fully integrated:

- **State (Taiwan):** Uses empowering policies without cultural domination.
- **Institution (MUIS):** Uses standards to connect businesses with consumers.
- **Legal Entity (Araya):** Develops transparent services connecting families, religion, and the state.

These cases not only reflect the power of the CBP framework but also align with Islamic principles such as *maqāṣid al-sharīah* (protecting dignity and justice) and *fiqh al-muāmalāt* (promoting transparent and peaceful coexistence) (Kamali, 2008; Auda, 2010). This confirms that Living Soft Infrastructure is not rooted solely in Western theory but also reflects faith-based values, making the proposition relevant both academically and practically.

3.7. Legal Entity Confirmation

Araya Nikah Social Enterprise Co., Ltd. is a registered social enterprise under Thailand's Social Enterprise Promotion Act B.E. 2562 (2019). It has received innovation funding from the National Innovation Agency (NIA) and collaborates with the Central Islamic Council of Thailand (CICOT) and the Department of Consular Affairs, Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), on the recognition of Nikah ceremonies and international marriage documentation.

4. Conclusion, Discussion, and Recommendations

This research establishes that Cultural-Based Practitioners (CBP) are not merely a theoretical construct but a **mediating mechanism** for transforming faith and cultural capital into tangible socio-economic outcomes. The simultaneous integration of cultural skills, cultural bridging, and cultural governance is essential to create a Living Soft Infrastructure. The absence of any one component can lead to "negative social capital," such as prejudice, exclusion, or domination.

4.1. Summary of Findings

The valorization of faith-based capital is a continuous process in culturally contested spaces, enacted by everyday individuals (e.g., restaurant staff, teachers) and entrepreneurs alike. However, this study identifies a **growth ceiling**: while individuals and organizations can drive this transformation to a certain point, complex issues necessitate engagement with institutions and the state to scale the Living Soft Infrastructure.

4.2. Discussion

The CBP framework functions as both an **evaluative tool** and a **service design model**.

- **At the individual level**, it builds trust and reduces prejudice.
- **At the institutional level**, it raises standards for services that integrate faith with the economy.
- **At the state level**, it creates policy environments conducive to coexistence.

A key finding is that the three CBP components are interdependent; a deficiency in one can produce negative outcomes. The concept of a "growth ceiling"—where the complexity of a problem outstrips the capacity of an individual or organization, requiring institutional scaffolding—is a novel contribution to the existing literature.

4.3. Research Limitations

While this study reflects real-world dynamics, its autoethnographic approach is inherently subjective. The framework has not yet been tested across a wide range of societies. Comparative research is needed to validate the applicability of the CBP concept in different contexts.

4.4. Policy Recommendations

To empower CBP sustainably, a **bottom-up policy approach** is recommended:

1. **External Outcome Verification:** Formally recognize the socio-economic outcomes generated by individuals and groups. This would reduce their burden of self-validation and increase credibility.
2. **Promote CBP Networks:** Support peer-to-peer collaboration between individuals, institutions, and state actors to reduce costs and build collective capacity.
3. **Fund Innovative Pilots:** Provide resources for CBPs to develop new methods based on their field experience without disrupting their core activities.
4. **Integration with Public Services:** Build an ecosystem that fosters CBP growth by integrating them into public services and ASEAN-level networks, while maintaining flexibility and respect for cultural diversity.

4.5. Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on developing **preliminary indicators** to measure the transformation of faith-based capital in contested spaces, focusing on metrics for trust, socio-economic outcomes, and network sustainability. Cross-regional comparative studies (e.g., in Europe, Africa, and the Middle East) are needed to test the potential of CBP as a universally applicable framework beyond ASEAN.

The integration of Western literature with Islamic concepts like *maqāṣid al-sharīah* is not intended to confine the CBP framework to a single religious community. Rather, it is to affirm that foundational values such as justice, transparency, and peaceful coexistence are universal. The ultimate goal of this research is to propose a "common language" for creating assessable service systems that can drive sustainable coexistence on a global scale.

References

Araya Nikah Social Enterprise Co., Ltd. (2025). *Internal reports: Pre-Nikah curriculum, ESG report, and Family of Peace ToC* [Internal document, not publicly available].

Auda, J. (2010). *Maqasid al-Shariah as philosophy of Islamic law: A systems approach*. International Institute of Islamic Thought.

Battour, M., & Ismail, M. N. (2016). Halal tourism: Concepts, practices, challenges and future. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 19, 150–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2015.12.008>

Bochner, A. P., & Ellis, C. (2016). *Evocative autoethnography: Writing lives and telling stories*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315545417>

Bourdieu, P. (1986). The forms of capital. In J. G. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of theory and research for the sociology of education* (pp. 241–258). Greenwood.

Deardorff, D. K. (2006). Identification and assessment of intercultural competence as a student outcome of internationalization. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 10(3), 241–266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315306287002>

Ellis, C. (2004). *The ethnographic I: A methodological novel about autoethnography*. AltaMira Press.

Hong Kong Trade Development Council. (2023, September 25). *ASEAN: US\$2.7 trillion digital economy pact planned to boost trade (DEFA)*. HKTDC Research. <https://research.hktdc.com/en/article/MTQ4NzIyOTQ1OA>

Islamic Religious Council of Singapore. (2020). *Annual report 2019/2020*. MUIS. <https://www.muis.gov.sg/Resources/Publications/Annual-Reports>

Islamic Religious Council of Singapore. (2021). *Halal certification and services overview*. MUIS. <https://www.muis.gov.sg/Halal/Overview>

Kamali, M. H. (2008). *Shari'ah law: An introduction*. Oneworld Publications.

Kymlicka, W. (2015). Solidarity in diverse societies: Beyond neoliberal multiculturalism and welfare chauvinism. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 3(17), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-015-0017-4>

Lederach, J. P. (1997). *Building peace: Sustainable reconciliation in divided societies*. United States Institute of Peace Press.

Maguire, J. S., & Matthews, J. (2012). Are we all cultural intermediaries now? An introduction to cultural intermediaries in context. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 15(5), 551–562. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367549412445762>

Mastercard-CrescentRating. (2024). *Global Muslim Travel Index (GMTI) 2024*. <https://www.crescentrating.com/reports/global-muslim-travel-index-2024.html>

Ministry of Finance Singapore. (2020–2022). *Use of past reserves for COVID-19 support measures*. Government of Singapore. <https://www.mof.gov.sg>

Moore, M. H. (1995). *Creating public value: Strategic management in government*. Harvard University Press.

Putnam, R. D. (2000). *Bowling alone: The collapse and revival of American community*. Simon & Schuster.

Reuters. (2017, September 13). Singapore names Halimah Yacob first female president, but no election. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-singapore-politics-idUSKCN1BO0BK>

Sen, A. (1999). *Development as freedom*. Oxford University Press.

Taiwan Tourism Administration. (2025). *Muslim-friendly environment*. <https://eng.taiwan.net.tw/m1.aspx?sNo=0020308>

Thansettakij. (2022, October 1). *เปิดประวัติ “พาตีเมาะ สะดียามู” ผู้ว่าฯ หญิงมุสลิมคนแรกของไทย* [Revealing the history of "Pateemoh Sadeeyamu," the first female Muslim governor of Thailand]. Thansettakij. <https://www.thansettakij.com>

The Standard. (2022, October 1). *ประวัติพาตีเมาะ สะดียามู: ผู้ว่าฯ ปัตตานีคนแรกที่เป็นผู้หญิงมุสลิม* [History of Pateemoh Sadeeyamu: The first governor of Pattani who is a Muslim woman]. The Standard. <https://www.thestandard.co>

The Straits Times. (2017, September 14). Halimah Yacob sworn in as Singapore's first woman president. *The Straits Times*.
<https://www.straitstimes.com>

United Nations Development Programme. (2022). *Human development report 2021/2022: Uncertain times, unsettled lives – Shaping our future in a transforming world*. UNDP.
<https://www.un-ilibrary.org/content/books/9789210016407>